

IDENTIFICATION OF ANISOTROPIC DAMAGE ON CFRP TUBES USING COMPUTER TOMOGRAPHY AND AUTOMATED ANALYSIS METHODS

L. Kroll¹, H. Ehrlinspiel², A. Czech¹, S. Mueller¹

¹ Chemnitz University of Technology, Institute of Mechanical and Polymer Engineering, D-09126 Chemnitz, Germany

² Liebherr-Aerospace Lindenberg GmbH, D-88153, Lindenberg, Germany
slk@mb.tu-chemnitz.de

SUMMARY

Volume computer tomography (VCT) is an approved non destructive testing method, which offers the possibility to capture internal structural damage three-dimensionally. A new approach analyzes these data in combination with image processing algorithms to identify the anisotropic damage parameters of pre-damaged CFRP tubes for phenomenological models.

Keywords: CFRP, Anisotropic damage, Computer tomography, Image processing, Feature extraction

INTRODUCTION

The application of new failure criterions, like for example of the fracture-mode-concept (FMC) criterion by Cuntze or Puck, permits to describe the failure behavior of fiber reinforced plastics (FRP) realistically and hence to avoid material-intensive dimensioning of FRP constructions [1, 2]. In accordance with these physically based failure criterions the basis failure modes: fiber failure (FF) and inter fiber failure (IFF) take combined loading types (tension, compression and shear) into account. Hence, these criterions consider the different anisotropic failure mechanisms corresponding to phenomenological fracture configuration on composites [3, 4]. For the verification of the criterions and for the improvement of the computation models with multilayered composite structures the application of sectional view-giving procedures, like for example of the computer tomography in combination with the digital image processing, offers special advantages. Thus the dangerous damages within composite structures due to crash and impact, which arise usually only unidentified in the internal structure, can be detected on the basis of non destructive testing methods [5]. This damage can have negative effects on structural integrity, and potentially lead to catastrophic failure. It is important to identify the damage non-destructively. By means of volume computer tomography the internal structure damage is first taken up as sectional view and then reconstructed three-dimensional. The application of automated digital image processing is essential in order to understand the multiplicity of the break phenomena in its location, kind and orientation.

1. EXPERIMENTAL

1.1. Materials and damage initiation

The tubular structures examined in this study were all manufactured using the filament winding process. The cylinders have an internal diameter of 32 mm and a wall thickness of 3.2 mm consisting of a $[\pm\omega]_{4S}$ stacking sequence lay-up. Samples for testing are 280 mm long and were damaged by using a pendulum impact test machine. The incident impact energy was controlled to low magnitude, so that the sample was not penetrated and only internal or barely visible damage occurred.

1.2. Computer tomography

Volume computer tomography (VCT) offers the possibility to capture internal structural damage three-dimensionally [6, 7]. This X-rays based imaging technology is well-established in medical diagnostics, but it is also a non-destructive testing method (NDT) for many industrial applications such as quality assurance, inspection method, reverse engineering [8] and more. Further examples can be found in [9, 10, 11]. VCT data investigated in this paper was created at Fraunhofer Entwicklungszentrum Röntgentechnik (EZRT) by using a cone-beam tomography consisting of a 225 kV microfocus X-ray source, an object slide and a 2048 x 2048 pixel flat panel detector.

1.3. Data acquisition

The CT investigation was performed on pre-damaged CFRP tubes. Due to the relationship of voxel resolution and object size (see Fig. 1 - left) the examined range was limited to a volume of about 36 mm x 36 mm x 28 mm (1600 projections per scan, scanning time ~72 min). So the reconstructed data has a resolution of 17.53 $\mu\text{m}/\text{voxel}$. The commercially available software (Volume Player Plus) has generated 2D-slices in x,y-plane with a series of 1579 images in z-direction (see Fig. 1 - right).

Figure 1: Voxel resolution vs. typical object size in dependence of X-ray source [10]; (Right:) Resolution of slices 2047 x 2047 (x,y-plane) and number of reconstructed 2D images (1579, z-direction) recorded on a micro-focus computer tomograph.

1.4. 3D computed tomography data

Visual inspection and measurement of surface defects are insufficient because they do not reveal the extent of matrix and fiber cracks within the laminate. The micro-CT reconstruction of investigated samples allows to observe an internal structural damage (Fig. 2). Because of the object-size-dependent resolution, it is not possible to separate the individual plies and also individual carbon fibers. Consequently, it is possible to recognize the rough geometry of cracks and delamination, but not to assign the damage to specified layer. Fig. 2a)-2c) shows a computer tomography volumetric reconstruction of a sample. Two distinct damage modes are apparent on the reconstruction; delamination and fiber fracture. Delamination appears to have occurred at every ply interface. Fiber fracture occurs at the point of impact and has propagated throughout the whole laminate depth. A connection is recognizable between the determined angle of the cracks, crack propagation direction and laminate lay-up. The manual analysis of CT data was done by partition every tenth slice at 16 areas and each of them has been separately rated on a scale of 1 to 6 (Fig. 2g). This method was related with a time-consuming work and provides only a rough approximation (Fig. 10a).

Figure 2: a), b), c) 3D volume 3D-micro-CT reconstruction; d), e), f) cross sectional slice (2D reconstruction); g) slice with selected areas for manual analysis.

2. AUTOMATED ANALYSIS OF CT-DATA

2.1. General Issues

Most commercial software packages for CT data have limited capabilities for extracting quantitative data characterizing the reconstructed structure. To investigate localized damage it is important to extract information like distributions, size and orientation of the damage structures. Because of noise and variations in intensity of 3D grey value data structure, the individual crack can't be easily identified from the whole CT-dataset. This paper presents a systematic approach to obtain this kind of information, using a special software tool created in the MATLAB environment. The algorithm of the program (Fig. 3) includes chosen Digital Image Processing operations and focuses on an

analysis of a large number of slices of the inspected specimen by utilizing quick and effective techniques. The newly-developed Computer-Tomography-based Damage Analysis System (CT-DAS) uses a sequence of slices, which were extracted from VCT data in x,y-plane and 256 grey levels, as input images. According to the introduced algorithm CT-DAS finds, locates and classifies internal damage structure. Details are discussed in sections 2.2.-2.4. The extracted information can be used for a finite element analysis (see section 2.5).

Figure 3: Flowchart of the Computer-Tomography-based Damage Analysis System (CT-DAS) program algorithm.

Figure 4: a) Flowchart of Computer-Tomography-based Damage Analysis (CT-DAS); b) CT-DAS main window.

2.2. Pre-Processing

The first step of image pre-processing of CT-DAS is to limit the data volume. A linear normalization with a following simple threshold operation permits to locate outlines of the investigated part effectively. The value profile of the line located in the center of the slice in x- and y- direction allows to crop the analyzed area of the image and to determine the optimal starting point P_d (1 for outer, 2 for inner contour) for tracing the outlines of the object (Fig. 5). The tracing process is done by using a MATLAB Image Processing Toolbox function [12]. The estimated edges allow to determine the center as well as the outside and internal radius of the tube.

Figure 5: Estimation of P_d coordinates using value profile of line (right).

2.3. Coordinate system definition

The calculated center of the analyzed part is equivalent with the center of the cylindrical coordinate system, the same coordinate system is used in the FE-Model. The analysis tool organizes the recognized damage data in the coordinate system of the finite element model. Therefore mesh parameters of the finite element model were applied to the scan procedure of the CT data.

Figure 6: a) Used cylindrical coordinate system; b) Analyzed area equal to finite element parameters.

2.4. Damage detection

The goal of the analysis is the description of a pre-damaged CFRP tube, defining the location, kind and size of internal structural damages for a finite element model. The identification of each kind of located damage is based on feature extraction, more information can be found in [12, 13]. Geometrical as well as gray-level features allow to classify the defects into three groups presented below (Fig. 7). A tangential oriented damage (see Fig. 7a) indicates delamination or inter fiber fracture (IFF), while a radial oriented damage (see Fig. 7b) shows a fracture through more than one (mostly through all) layers and indicates for example fiber fracture (FF). Small, round damages (Fig. 7c) were interpreted as pores and local inhomogeneities. In this way it is possible to separate each kind of damage or any combination of them and to give a more detailed description with the chosen kind of located damage. A further objective is to identify the fracture-modes described by Cuntze (see section 2.6.).

Figure 7: Automated detection of three damage types *a)* delamination or inter fiber fractur (IFF), *b)* fiber fracture and *c)* pores and local inhomogeneity.

2.5. Finite element modeling

In finite element models, the tubes are composed of transverse-isotropic plies neglecting the crossing points of filaments caused by manufacturing process. The characteristics of implemented material is given in Table 1 with brittle elastic behavior. Non-linearity of materials is not taken into account. We assume, that all plies are alternatively directed in $\pm\omega^\circ$.

Table 1: Material properties used for modeling.

Material	E_{11} (GPa)	E_{22} (GPa)	G_{12} (GPa)	ν_{12}
Carbon/Epoxy	125	8	3.8	0.28

The models presented here were studied by using ANSYS Rev. 11.0 [14]. Thereby the element library provides specific shell and solid elements with the so called "layered option" for the modeling of composites. Since the ratio of wall thickness to diameter ($t/d \sim 0.09$) has referred to a moderately-thick shell structure, the correct choice of an appropriate element type as well as a suitable element size and location of integration points resp. node location in consideration of given geometry is essential for precise numerical results. Therefore a benchmark test with different settings was performed in comparison to the analytical solution presented in [15], what is based on rotationally symmetric mechanical load with the material law in following pseudo-vectorial notation:

$$\begin{pmatrix} \varepsilon_r \\ \varepsilon_\phi \\ \varepsilon_z \\ \gamma_{\phi z} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} S_{11} & S_{12} & S_{13} & S_{14} \\ S_{12} & S_{22} & S_{23} & S_{24} \\ S_{13} & S_{23} & S_{33} & S_{34} \\ S_{14} & S_{24} & S_{34} & S_{44} \end{pmatrix} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} \sigma_r \\ \sigma_\phi \\ \sigma_z \\ \tau_{\phi z} \end{pmatrix}$$

with S_{ij} ($i, j = 1, 2, 3, 4$) as compliances.

In accordance with the above-mentioned analytical solution, the SHELL181 element gives the adequate mechanical response for local in-plane characteristics for torque loads and – for that reason – is chosen for further investigations in this paper. But as the element formulation is governed by the first order shear deformation theory (usually

referred as Mindlin-Reissner shell theory) and its corresponding assumptions it has to mention that the SHELL181 element loses information in z-direction, i.e. σ_z - stress component.

For a practical finite element modeling of a pre-damaged structure the description of material degradation behavior using continuum damage mechanics (CDM) is very advisable. In this case of plane stress conditions the constitutive model of Matzenmiller et al. [16] can be used. Here \mathbf{D} represents the damage operator

$$\mathbf{D} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{1-D_{11}} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{1}{1-D_{22}} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{1-D_s} \end{bmatrix}$$

The degradation variables D_{11} and D_{22} denote the damage in the two principle axis of each UD-layer. An additional degradation variable, D_s , is introduced to characterize the modification of the shear behavior. The degradation parameters D_{11} and D_{22} need to be verified separately for the tension and compression domain. The constitutive law for the damaged state then results in

$$\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} = \mathbf{S}^0 \mathbf{D} \boldsymbol{\sigma} = \tilde{\mathbf{S}} \boldsymbol{\sigma}$$

where \mathbf{S}^0 denotes the compliance matrix at the initial state. The effective compliance matrix $\tilde{\mathbf{S}}$ is not the correct mathematical matrix multiplication. Only under the assumptions of Matzenmiller et al. [16] the effective compliance matrix becomes

$$\tilde{\mathbf{S}} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{S_{11}}{1-D_{11}} & S_{12} & 0 \\ S_{21} & \frac{S_{22}}{1-D_{22}} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{S_{66}}{1-D_s} \end{bmatrix}$$

Here, D_{11} could be interpreted as the damage variable for fiber damage. D_{22} should be interpreted as a crack density parameter. For an orthotropic layer, the shear compliance is independent of the residual compliances. Thus, the determination of shear damage by the parameter D_s is a direct consequence of the definition of the constitutive equation.

2.6. Failure mode concept (FMC)

For the application of failure-mode-based strength criteria Cuntze [17] has adopted basic considerations of Hashin [18] and introduced the special invariants I_i ($i = 1, 2, \dots, 5$), that are invariant referring to an optional rotation around the axis in direction of fiber:

$$\begin{aligned} I_1 &= \sigma_1 & I_4 &= (\sigma_2 - \sigma_3)^2 + 4\tau_{23}^2 \\ I_2 &= \sigma_2 + \sigma_3 & I_5 &= (\sigma_2 - \sigma_3)(\tau_{31}^2 - \tau_{21}^2) - 4\tau_{23}\tau_{31}\tau_{21} \\ I_3 &= \tau_{31}^2 + \tau_{21}^2 \end{aligned}$$

In contrast to the action plane concept (APC) by Puck [19], which is based on the extreme value theory, the failure mode concept (FMC) by Cuntze is composed by special invariants and considers 5 different failure modes (see Table 2). Details including material behavior, three free curve parameters ($b_{\perp\parallel}, b_{\perp}^{\tau}, b_{\perp\parallel}^{\tau}$) and more are given in [1].

Table 2: Failure Modes and failure conditions classified by Cuntze [1].

Fiber Fracture (FF)	Inter Fiber Fracture (IFF)
<p>IFF3:</p> $F_{\perp}^{\tau} = (b_{\perp}^{\tau} - 1) \cdot \frac{I_2}{R_{\perp}^{(-)}} + \frac{b_{\perp}^{\tau} \cdot I_4 + b_{\perp\parallel}^{\tau} \cdot I_3}{(R_{\perp}^{(-)})^2} = 1$	

2.7. Results and Discussion

Volume Computer Tomography (VCT) generates large data for the investigation of internal structure damages. The manual observation of these 3D data is time-consuming and leads to subjective results. Therefore a systematic approach to obtain an automated analysis method for large VCT data was developed on basis of 2D digital image processing. By processing the 2D images in an enormous series the third dimension is mounted on the analysis, too. Furthermore the extraction of damage distribution, size and orientation motivated by Cuntze's fracture-mode-concept was focused in this study. With the present VCT data it is possible to classify three different fracture types corresponding to composite materials: i) delamination or inter fiber fracture (IFF), ii) fiber fracture and iii) pores and local inhomogeneity. The possibility to separate these kinds of damage opens new opportunities to investigate them and the interactions between them. This automated analysis method allows an accurate and direct comparison of the results as well as a detailed investigation (see Fig. 10). This exact description of the object structure leads to the prediction of damage parameters and has a positive influence to the preciseness of finite element simulation and other applications. For calibration of CT-DAS a finite element simulation based on simplified damaged parameters was compared with experimental torque tests. The calculated torsional stiffness by finite element analysis confirms the main trends shown by the experimental results with an relative deviation less than 12%.

Figure 8: *a)* Tomography volumetric reconstruction of a damaged CFRP tube; Finite element model with damage extracted from computer tomography reconstruction by manual analysis (*b)* and automated analysis (*c*).

3. CONCLUSIONS

For detection and classification of existing structure damage within FRP components a software was developed on the basis of image processing algorithms using the MATLAB environment. Therefore digital images of volume computer tomography are input data for the classification of real arising failure modes. An evaluation of the local damage and thus the FRP degradation can be made by such an identification of the failure modes, which flow into appropriate finite element models. With the following global finite-elements analysis in combination with the implemented failure-mode-based "degradation elements" the remaining mechanical behavior of the composite structure can be determined concerning stiffness and strength.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors gratefully acknowledge the financial support of this research by Bundesministerium für Wirtschaft und Technologie within the Luftfahrtforschungsprogramm IV.

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